

Health Policy Values

Health Policy Values

Personal Values and Spiritual Beliefs

As a Christian, I believe in one God, who is merciful and just. I also believe in the concept of heaven and hell after death. I believe that Jesus Christ is the son of God, as well as, the messiah, which is the ultimate savior of humanity. Holy books, on which my faith is dependent is the old testament that is the Hebrew Scripture and the New Testament, which is the continuation of the Old Testament.

Personal Beliefs and Opinions about Health Care Policy

My personal beliefs and opinions about the health care policy can be analyzed in terms of the following three factors:

Cost

All the catholic Christians should participate in protecting their lives by the end. In order to do so, they should refuse euthanasia and skeptically weight their commitment to participate in the medical treatment, which should not just be the ordinary care but something more than that (HCC, 2009). Death should not be intended and measures should be taken to avoid it no matter how heavy the costs are. Although, natural death is the final step towards the eternal context of human life but human beings should pay the worldly costs to attain good health (Alberta Health Services, n.d).

Quality

Health policy says that quality health should be provided to all the citizens of the country. According to Christianity, quality faithfulness of God is in exploring life and living quality life. This quality life means that every Christian should have access to hygienic food, clothes, accommodation, etc. dirt and other kinds of unhygienic things should be avoided by Christians in every walk of life (Edgar, n.d).

Social Issues

Health and fitness teachers should lead their lives independent of the religious belief, values and practices, along with the traditions. Every Christian should respond to a social issue without keeping in mind their religious identity. This means that all Christians should care for humanity. Health facilities and quality health products should be provided to all the people of the society, no matter they are Christians or they belong to any other faith/religion (Anonymous, n.d).

Factors Effecting Personal Perspective on Health Care Policy**Upbringing**

Positive upbringing makes a person provide health care facilities to each and every human in the society.

Spiritual/Religious Doctrine

Biblical references reveal that Jesus Christ use to pray of health and prosperity for people, who were not even Christians. Moreover, he also used to pray for his enemies.

Personal & Professional Experiences

Personally, I believe that Christianity teaches people to do fair with everyone and I have seen such people always remain healthy and happy in life, who care for each individual health equally.

Political Ideology

I believe, that political ideology also favors that every health care provider should give equal health opportunities to everyone (Storm, 2003). Like Christianity, ever religion has these values as their basic ones (NHS, n.d). Every religion gives the message of giving equal health to all the people of the society (Frantti, 1993).

Inconsistencies related to Personal Beliefs on Health Policy

I usually observe that some people try to give services to others if they belong to their own faith. This practice should be discouraged politically, socially and religiously in the society. This will create fairness and justice in the society and every civil group shall be satisfied.

References

- Alberta Health Services. (n.d). *Health Care and Religious Beliefs*. Data Retrieved from <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/ps-1026227-health-care-religious-beliefs.pdf>
- Anonymous. (n.d). *Curriculum for Excellence: Religious and Moral Education Principles and Practice*. Data Retrieved from https://www.educationscotland.gov.uk/Images/rme_principles_practice_tcm4-540203.pdf
- Anonymous. (n.d). *Health Care and Religious Beliefs*. Data Retrieved from <http://lomalindahealth.org/media/medical-center/departments/employee-wholeness/healthcare-religious-beliefs.pdf>
- Edgar, B. (n.d). *Eight Core Christian Values*. Data Retrieved from <http://www.ethos.org.au/Site/Ethos/filesystem/documents/in-depth/Politics/Eight+Core+Christian+Values+-+Brian+Edgar.pdf>
- Frantti, J. (1993). *Christian Values in a Changing Society*. Data Retrieved from <http://llchurch.org/topics/valuessociety1.pdf>
- HCC. (2009). *A Dictionary of Patients' Spiritual & Cultural Values for Health Care Professionals*. Data Retrieved from <http://www.healthcarechaplaincy.org/userimages/doc/Cultural%20Dictionary.pdf>
- NHS. (n.d). *Religious, Spiritual, Pastoral and Cultural Care*. Data Retrieved from http://www.sdhct.nhs.uk/pdf_docs/cultureandreligionhandbook.pdf
- Storm, I. (2013). "Christianity is not Just about Religion": Religious and National Identities in a Northern English Town. *Secularism and Nonreligion*. Data Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=9&cad=rja&uac>

[t=8&ved=0CE4QFjAI&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.secularismandnonreligion.org%2Farticle%2Fdownload%2Fsnr.aj%2F10&ei=ZfgjVMvKK8OV7Aam74GYDQ&usg=AFQjCNGHxvTj9avjk_7OhpQKL70S74YwhQ&bvm=bv.76247554,d.d2s](http://www.secularismandnonreligion.org/)